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Measurements of the CKM angle γ at LHCb

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Abstract

A standard candle measurement of CP violation in the Standard Model is the tree-level determination of the CKM angle γ . These proceedings present recent time-integrated LHCb measurements of CP violation, as well as the latest γ and charm mixing combination. The analyses presented make use of beauty to open charm decays, which supersede previous Run 1 measurements using the full LHCb Run 1 and Run 2 dataset or are performed for the first time at LHCb in new decay channels.

1 Introduction

An important place to look for physics beyond the Standard Model is within the interaction of the quarks, which is described by the Cabibbo–Kobayashi–Maskawa (CKM) matrix [1, 2]. Its unitarity can be represented in the complex plane by a particular triangle, where one of the angles is the weak phase $\gamma \equiv \arg(-V_{ud}V_{ub}^*/V_{cd}V_{cb}^*)$, which is the only angle easily accessible at tree level. Given that all hadronic parameters can be determined directly from data, the theoretical uncertainty on γ is negligible. This is the reason why direct tree-level measurements of γ are standard candle measurements of the Standard Model. On the other hand, New Physics is expected to potentially contribute through loop processes, which are inputs of global fits to the unitary triangle, for which a closed triangle is assumed. The indirect determination of γ , which is more precise than the direct measurement, gives a current value of $\gamma = (65.5_{-2.7}^{+1.1})^\circ$ [3]. The latest γ and charm LHCb combination [4] yields a value of $\gamma = (63.8_{-3.7}^{+3.5})^\circ$, which is the most precise measurement from a single experiment to date and shown in Fig. 1 (left) for the different B modes used as inputs for the combination. In order to be able to make a comparison and look for any discrepancy between the two measurements, the aim is to improve the precision of direct determinations of γ . This is one of the key goals of the LHCb experiment, which can be achieved by combining results to improve the overall sensitivity to the CP -violating phase γ .

Figure 1: One-dimensional profile likelihood obtained for γ using different B modes (left) and two-dimensional profile likelihood contours obtained for different D decay modes contributing to the latest LHCb combination (right).

The golden mode for such measurements is $B^\pm \rightarrow DK^\pm$, with $D \rightarrow K_S^0 h^+ h^-$, which is the most precise measurement obtained from a single analysis [5]. Different families of D decay modes are used, as illustrated in Fig. 1 (right). It can be seen that modes of the type $D \rightarrow h^+ h^-$ give narrow but multiple solutions, while the self-conjugate $D \rightarrow K_S^0 h^+ h^-$ decays provide a wide single solution. This can be seen more clearly from previous combinations such as in Ref. [6]. This is due to the equations relating the measured CP observables in the corresponding analyses to the physics parameters of interest. In these proceedings, the latest results from LHCb using self-conjugate D decay modes are presented.

2 Measuring γ in three-body self-conjugate final states

Direct measurements of γ are performed in $B^\pm \rightarrow DK^\pm$, with $D \rightarrow K_S^0 h^+ h^-$, where the D meson is a superposition of D^0 and \bar{D}^0 states. Both states should be able to decay to the same final state in which they are reconstructed. This provides an interference between $b \rightarrow c\bar{u}s$ and $b \rightarrow u\bar{c}s$ transitions, from which the sensitivity to the angle γ is obtained. Three-body self-conjugate final states [7–9] such as $K_S^0 \pi^+ \pi^-$ and $K_S^0 K^+ K^-$ are used. The kinematics of these decays,

which form complex systems of resonances, can be fully described in two dimensions in a Dalitz plot [10], whose coordinates are the invariant masses $m_+ \equiv m(K_S^0 h^+)$ and $m_- \equiv m(K_S^0 h^-)$. The interference effects appear as different distributions, between B^- and B^+ decays, of the D meson Dalitz plot. Because the strong-phase difference δ_D varies across the Dalitz plot, the phase space is binned and the differences are observed by performing a counting experiment in each of the bins. The yields in each bin N_i^\pm obtained can then be interpreted by using the following equations [11]:

$$\begin{aligned} N_i^- &= h_B^- [F_i + (x_-^2 + y_-^2) F_{-i} + 2\sqrt{F_i F_{-i}} (c_i x_- + s_i y_-)], \\ N_i^+ &= h_B^+ [F_{-i} + (x_+^2 + y_+^2) F_i + 2\sqrt{F_i F_{-i}} (c_i x_+ - s_i y_+)]. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In each bin, the fractional yield of flavour-tagged D^0 decays is represented by the coefficient F_i . The amplitude weighted averages of the strong-phase differences in the bins $c_i = \cos(\Delta\delta_D)$, $s_i = \sin(\Delta\delta_D)$ are measured directly at BESIII [12] and CLEO [13], and h_B^\pm represent the normalisation factors. In this way, the CP observables x_\pm, y_\pm , directly related to the physics parameters of interest through $x_\pm + iy_\pm = r_B \cdot e^{i(\delta_B \pm \gamma)}$, can be extracted from a fit to the measured yields.

3 Measurement of γ in $B^0 \rightarrow DK^{*0}, D \rightarrow K_S^0 h^+ h^-$

The first recent measurement of γ presented uses $B^0 \rightarrow DK^{*0}, D \rightarrow K_S^0 h^+ h^-$ decays [14] and supersedes previous results published by LHCb in this decay channel. As described above, the measurement of γ is performed in phase-space bins of the D decay. The mass fit is performed simultaneously in each bin in order to determine the CP observables, as illustrated for particular bins in Fig. 2 which are chosen to highlight the CP asymmetry.

Figure 2: Fit example in particular Dalitz plot bins, chosen to highlight the CP asymmetry, for \bar{B}^0 (left) and B^0 (right) candidates.

Due to limited statistics, CP violation in these modes is yet to be established. The physics parameters are interpreted from the measured CP observables x_\pm, y_\pm , obtaining the values $\gamma = (49_{-18}^{+23})^\circ$, $\delta_{B^0} = (236_{-21}^{+19})^\circ$ and $r_{B^0} = (0.271_{-0.068}^{+0.068})$. These results are model independent, using the strong-phase inputs c_i, s_i from CLEO and BESIII. The value of γ is consistent with the LHCb combination, where the best-fit value for γ determined from B^0 modes is $\gamma = (82.0_{-8.8}^{+8.1})^\circ$. Therefore, the result obtained in this analysis will reduce the difference between the values obtained using B^\pm and B^0 modes, as can be seen in Fig. 1 (left) in the latest LHCb combination.

4 Measurement of γ in $B^\pm \rightarrow D^{*0}h^\pm$, $D^{*0} \rightarrow D\pi^0/\gamma$, $D \rightarrow K_S^0 h^+ h^-$

The second analysis presented uses $B^\pm \rightarrow D^{*0}h^\pm$ decays, with $D^{*0} \rightarrow D\pi^0/\gamma$, $D \rightarrow K_S^0 h^+ h^-$ [15]. This constitutes the first measurement in these decays at LHCb, which is also performed in phase-space bins of the D meson decay. In this case, a two-dimensional fit to the invariant-mass distributions is needed in order to distinguish broad and overlapping shapes due to irreducible backgrounds that remain in the sample after the candidate selection. The invariant masses $m(D^0\pi^0/\gamma)$ and $m(D^0h^\pm)$ are used in order to measure the CP observables. In this analysis, all final-state particles are reconstructed and an additional phase shift of π between $D^{*0} \rightarrow D\pi^0$ and $D^{*0} \rightarrow D\gamma$ leads to opposite CP asymmetries for these decays. The likelihood contours for the CP observables x_\pm , y_\pm are presented in Fig. 3. The angle between the two vectors defined by the origin and the end-point coordinates (x_-, y_-) and (x_+, y_+) is equal to 2γ .

Figure 3: Two-dimensional likelihood contours obtained for the CP observables x_\pm , y_\pm .

Similarly to the previous measurement described, the physics parameters are determined to be $\gamma = (69 \pm 14)^\circ$, $\delta_B^{D^{*0}K} = (311 \pm 15)^\circ$ and $r_B^{D^{*0}K} = (0.15 \pm 0.03)$. These results are also model independent and consistent with the LHCb combination.

5 Study of CP violation in $B^\pm \rightarrow Dh^\pm$, $D \rightarrow K^+K^-\pi^+\pi^-$

The last analysis presented is the first study of CP violation in $B^\pm \rightarrow Dh^\pm$, $D \rightarrow K^+K^-\pi^+\pi^-$ decays [16], in bins of the D meson decay. Since this is a four-body decay, the phase space is five dimensional and the binning scheme is more complex than in the previous analyses presented. In this analysis, the required strong-phase parameters c_i , s_i are currently taken from an LHCb amplitude model. Similarly to the other analyses, an extended maximum-likelihood fit is performed to the invariant-mass distributions, as shown in Fig. 4 (left) for $B^\pm \rightarrow DK^\pm$. A second fit is performed simultaneously in each category defined by the phase-space bin and the B charge in order to measure the CP observables, and CP violation effects are observed through local asymmetries in bins. The results for the physics parameters are $\gamma = (116_{-14}^{+12})^\circ$, $\delta_B^{DK} = (81_{-13}^{+14})^\circ$ and $r_B^{DK} = (0.110_{-0.020}^{+0.020})$, which are model dependent. The confidence regions in the (δ_B, γ) space are presented in Fig. 4 (right), where the phase-space integrated measurement and the LHCb combination are also shown. Model-independent values of c_i , s_i , which are expected to be measured by BESIII, are required for a model-independent measurement from the binned asymmetries. This analysis is therefore planned to be performed in the future in order to obtain a model-independent determination of γ .

Figure 4: Invariant-mass distribution for $B^\pm \rightarrow DK^\pm$ with the fit result superimposed (left) and confidence regions in the (δ_B, γ) space obtained for $B^\pm \rightarrow DK^\pm$ (right).

6 Conclusion and outlook

Future γ combinations will include the recent model-independent results presented, which are expected to have a strong impact in the next combination as they combine with other measurements of γ from the same B decay channels. A future model-independent determination from $B^\pm \rightarrow Dh^\pm$, $D \rightarrow K^+K^-\pi^+\pi^-$ decays is also expected to be included in future combinations. The aim is to cover as many B and D decay combinations as possible to further improve the precision on γ , and ongoing analyses with the full Run 1 and Run 2 LHCb dataset, such as using $B^\pm \rightarrow DK^{*\pm}$ decays, are yet to be published. Using sub-dominant channels provides further constraints and important cross-checks, as different backgrounds and systematic uncertainties are involved in various channels.

Figure 5: Evolution of the CKM angle γ result from published LHCb combinations, where the central values and 1σ uncertainties are presented.

The LHCb expected sensitivity of about 4° for Run 1-2 was achieved and surpassed, as shown in Fig. 5, while further results are still to be published. As more data is collected during Run 3 and beyond, a more precise tree-level determination, better than 1° , is expected [17, 18] to be possible for the CKM angle γ , which is a standard candle measurement of CP violation in the Standard Model.

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